

PaNOSC key achievements

Making FAIR data a reality at photon & neutron (PaN) facilities

Coordinator: Partners:

EUROPEAN
SPALLATION
SOURCE

**PROJECT
COORDINATOR**

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**PROJECT
NUMBER**

823852

WEBSITE

www.panosc.eu

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PaNOSC has been driven by the goal to make FAIR data a reality at photon and neutron research facilities, developing and providing services for scientific data, and connecting these to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Background and Scope

Photon and Neutron (PaN) facilities are essential research infrastructures (RIs) for the understanding of matter and its properties. Together these facilities produce petabytes of data, which can give us a more complete picture of the world around us.

PaNOSC (and its sister project, ExPaNDS) have been working to make the data produced at PaN facilities easily accessible to the users and the public, by providing scientific data management for enabling Open Science.

A new PaN FAIR data policy framework allows PaN facilities to manage and curate data according to the FAIR principles, for data to be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

Main Goals and Objectives

Overall Concept

The overall approach implemented implied making the data available, as well as the data analysis software, contributing to Reproducible Science and FAIR data, and increasing the ability to find and inspect the data interactively.

Based on this approach, PaNOSC has provided:

- **Services to complement data, such as data management plans (DMPs) and services to perform data analysis, such as VISA.**
- **Open Source Software to share data analysis knowledge and expertise.**

The analysis software that has been used on the data set, and the expertise required to create it, is made available.

- **Inform and train scientists.**

To include software that has created the results shown in the manuscript as part of the publication, and include a description of how the software needs to be executed to compute the results as part of the publication.

Strategy

PaNOSC partners have set-up an analysis environment with analysis software available through a **data search portal** and **data analysis portal**. These are connected to the facility-specific services, such as authentication, metadata catalogues, file location information and remote analysis services.

Remote data analysis is now possible through VISA, the Virtual Infrastructure for Scientific Analysis, with Jupyter Notebooks, or remote Desktop technologies.

The **user experience** is now similar at all facilities. Data sources and services that are used as back-end to VISA are facility-specific.

Why FAIR Data?

Findable

Accessible

Interoperable

Reusable

PaNOSC has strived to give scientists better tools to fully exploit their data and facilitate the use of Open Data, working to unify the fragmented research data landscape with a common data policy framework and coherent set of services for data stewardship at Photon and Neutron (PaN) facilities and through the EOSC.

For whom?

Scientific and industrial users of PaN facilities, scientists and researchers from across disciplines, research infrastructures from different clusters, publishers, IT staff and managers, the wider public.

Science benefits

FAIR data is data which meets the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR). This means that, from data collection, to data processing, analysis, through to publication, data are curated and managed following FAIR principles, with the ultimate goal of **optimising the reuse of data**, also across scientific clusters and domains.

How?

The two sister projects, PaNOSC and ExPaNDS, have joined forces to setup the IT infrastructure and develop the policies for FAIR data stewardship, as well as the tools, software and services for (meta)data search, analysis, simulation and re-use, to enable the community of users of PaN facilities, and researchers across disciplines, to perform FAIR data science.

Data Policy and Stewardship

A new **PaN FAIR data policy framework**¹ has been published and adopted by all PaNOSC partners, in line with the EOSC activities on data policy harmonisation. The policy ensures that FAIR principles are applied as broadly as possible. To facilitate the process, guidelines for Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), long-term archiving, and legal aspects linked to FAIR data, GDPR and data federation have been published.

A **Data Management Plan** template for experiments performed at the PaNOSC research infrastructures has also been defined and developed.

PaNOSC partners

Federated PaN Data Catalogue

What makes PaN data FINDABLE and ACCESSIBLE?

- **Search API** for federated access to FAIR data sources of different PaN Research Infrastructures regardless of source and location.
- Specific metadata schemes and search dictionaries, to enable domain-specific searches across the PaNOSC data repositories.
- **OAI-PMH protocol** for indexing metadata and data by OpenAIRE / re3data and B2Find.

What makes PaN data REUSABLE?

- **NeXus/HDF5** - metadata and data format community standard.
- **Electronic logbooks** capturing what happens during experiments, and keeping track of the steps & settings of the experiments for future usage.
- **DOIs** (Digital Object Identifiers) for each experiment and for one or more datasets, to be cited in publications.

European Photon and Neutron (PaN) Open Data Search Portal

The PaN Data Portal federates PaN metadata catalogues and data repositories to **facilitate searching, finding and downloading open data across most PaN RIs in Europe.**

Who is the federated search API for?

The portal and federated search API enables PaN researchers to develop applications that leverage integrated access to PaN research data. This can have a positive impact on their competitiveness. Likewise, the federated API facilitates the integration of data from Research Infrastructures with data of other RIs as part of a unified FAIR data infrastructure.

Data repositories

PaNOSC partners are committed to storing raw data produced by users at the research facilities and making it available as Open Data once the embargo period is over.

VISA - Virtual Infrastructure for Scientific Analysis

VISA offers data analysis and simulation capabilities using remote desktops or Jupyter Notebooks interfaces, enabling users to **remotely analyse data** from PaN facilities during or after their experiments. Depending on the setup of the facility, VISA can also provide instrument remote control.

WATCH THE VIDEO
<https://bit.ly/VISA-video>

VISA is a new way for academic and industrial researchers to access data and advanced analysis tools from wherever they are.

VISA is useful in different roles:

- Data analysis, coupled with a Jupyterlab notebooks.
- Real time collaboration, with the help of a local expert.
- Accessing data without needing to download them.

Some services available either via VISA or standalone:

- **H5Web**: web-base viewers for Nexus/HDF5 files
- **Jupyter Hub** and **Jupyter-slurm**: infrastructure for remote execution of notebooks on the computing and data infrastructure of the facility.

Who is VISA for?

The VISA platform, by providing an integrated environment for analysing PaN related datasets based on popular tools like remote desktops and Jupyter notebooks, leverages the FAIR principles of the PaN data to enable scientists run analysis experiments. The environment offers support for real time collaboration through data sharing. It has a major impact on researchers of the PaN community, through increasing their scientific capacity and productivity.

Source code and documentation

- Source code:
<https://github.com/ILLGrenoble>
- VISA deployment documentation:
<https://readthedocs.org/projects/visa/>

Typical workflow for Common Portal usage

User authentication using Umbrella ID

Search for datasets (for which the user has been a proposal member, thus requiring authenticated access)

Selection of an analysis environment (in either a remote desktop, or Jupyter Notebook environment)

Spawn the chosen analysis environment and link it to the chosen datasets

Access the environment via the Portal and perform data analysis

EOSC integration

VISA is now accessible via the EOSC portal to provide federated data analysis of data at each facility.

<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/visa-virtual-infrastructure-for-scientific-analysis>

OSCOVIDA

During the pandemic, OSCOVIDA was developed within PaNOSC. It is a citizen science prototype environment developed for remote and reproducible data analysis of COVID 19 infection data

<https://oscovida.github.io>

Simulation Data Services

The **Virtual Neutron and x-ray Laboratory - ViNYL** offers services for simulation and modelling of PaN sources, beamlines and experimental instruments, as well as start-to-end simulations to describe entire experiments at PaN facilities.

Who is ViNYL for?

As for most of the PaNOSC services, ViNYL is designed for users of PaN facilities. It is also a useful tool for PhD students and young researchers while preparing for experiments, as well as for RIs' staff, both for designing and setting up new instruments, or during operations.

Why ViNYL?

ViNYL enables PaN users to rapidly implement simulation and analysis workflows specific to their facilities, instruments, and experiments. This is important, as simulations of the various parts and processes involved in complex experiments play an increasingly important role in the entire lifecycle of scientific data generated at RIs: from the idea for an experiment (often triggered by results from numerical and theoretical work), via design and optimisation of experimental setups, estimation of experimental artifacts, generation of supporting material for beamtime proposals, assisting in decision making during an ongoing experiment, through to interpretation of experimental data, data analysis, and finally drawing insights from the obtained results, which then lead to new experiments.

ViNYL Software Packages

McStasScript

Simulation code McStas, world leading in simulation of instrumentation for neutron scattering and virtual neutron scattering experiments.

<https://github.com/PaNOSC-ViNYL/McStasScript>

McStas capabilities

McStas is capable of simulating much more than just optics, it can for example be used to investigate sample environment and perform full virtual experiments. Below are a few animations made using McStas showing a diamond anvil pressure experiment with one of the diamonds being rotated.

OASYS

Open-source graphical environment for x-ray virtual experiments.

<https://oasys-kit.github.io/>

SIMEX

Photon experiment simulation environment.

<https://github.com/PaNOSC-ViNYL/SimEx>

Plot radial projection as a function of q

```
In [12]: analyzer.plotRadialProjection(logscale=True, offset=0, unit="q^-1")
WARNING:pyFAI:DEPRECATION: function, AzimuthalIntegrator is deprecated since silx version 0.16! Use 'pyFAI.AzimuthalIntegrator.AzimuthalIntegrator' instead.
File ~/gpps/exfel/data/user/juncheng/miniconda3/envs/simex0.5/lib/python3.7/site-packages/SimEx/Analysis/Diffractio
nAnalysis.py, line 529, in azimuthalIntegration
    wavelength=1md*1e-9)
WARNING:silx.openc1.common:Unable to import pyOpenCL. Please install it from: http://pypi.python.org/pypi/pyopencl
```


E-learning platform

The PaN e-learning platform hosts free education and training for scientists and students on scientific topics related to PaN science.

The platform, accessible via <https://e-learning.pan-training.eu/>, hosts free education and training for scientists and students, with online interactive courses on both the theory of photon and neutron science, and how to use python code or software for data reduction and modelling.

Both Jupyter and OASYS have been integrated into the platform, which can be accessed via a single sign-on using the federated AAI, UmbrellaID.

Create a new account, or access using your UmbrellaID or ORCID credentials.

Who is the e-learning platform for?

The PaN e-learning platform is specifically designed to provide training for users of PaN sources. The platform provides curated educational content to help users of research infrastructures learn about specific scattering methods and data analysis techniques. Thus, it is a useful platform for PaN users, researchers and research groups, as well as scientists giving lectures to early-stage researchers, and lecturers from academic institutions.

How does the e-learning platform work?

The PaN e-learning platform is based on the **Moodle learning management system** used by many universities and schools around the world. Moodle allows teachers to follow students' progress, create quizzes with immediate feedback and include interactive H5P content. Videos, written notes and links to third-party content can also be included.

The most unique part of pan-learning is the ability to **attach Jupyter notebooks to a course**, an excellent way for scientists to demonstrate how their data reduction and analysis works.

A JupyterHub container can be launched from a course page, which runs on servers at the ESS. The container pulls notebooks directly from a teacher's github page, so if changes are made there, the course updates automatically. Having the notebooks run remotely is perfect for introducing python-based techniques to those unfamiliar with it.

PaN-learning also has a **wiki**, which does not require a log-on to access. There you will find wikipedia-style articles on the theory of neutron science, along with exercises to test understanding.

In addition to the e-learning platform, a **training catalogue** developed by ExPaNDS for PaN science allows browsing instructional material and resources from institutes around Europe.

<https://e-learning.pan-training.eu/>

EOSC Integration

Most PaNOSC services have been added to the service catalogue in the EOSC Portal, and are now provided and accessible via the EOSC. Where necessary, a **single federated AAI - Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure service (Umbrella ID)**, enables users to log in to multiple applications and websites with one single set of credentials.

Specifically, the PaN services onboarded to the EOSC Portal are the following:

- **PaNOSC Software Catalogue**, with over a hundred standard software tools used for analysing data from PaN RIs;
- **Human Organ Atlas**: an open data portal of 3D scans of human organs with micron resolution for different pathologies, including COVID-19.
- **PaNOSC open data portal**
- **PaNOSC e-learning platform**, hosting free education and training for scientists and students
- **Data search API service**

Sustainability

PaNOSC has been constantly interacting with stakeholders, and contributing to shape the EOSC.

Sustainability has been a core issue since the project's start. A number of services developed by PaNOSC are being integrated into the core business activities of the facilities and will need to be sustained. Certain fundamental objectives, such as FAIR data and Open Science, will change the way the facilities work and will be considered the new norm.

Where additional costs are incurred by EOSC users, these have been collected and are being used to produce a **business model** and a formal long-term mission and vision for the sustainability of the PaNOSC infrastructure and software developed.

As also stated in the LEAPS roadmap¹ presented to the EC in June 2022, investments in sustaining and strengthening open science activities are needed to develop the federated service PaN Open Data Commons as an essential component of EOSC for showcasing and accessing data.

¹https://leaps-initiative.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/LEAPS-ESAPS-Brochure_final-20052022-3.pdf

Peer-reviewed publications

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- A. Götz, J. Bodera Sempere, A. Campbell, A. de Maria, M. del Rio, R. Dimper, J. Kieffer, A. Solé, T. Vincent; S. Caunt, J. Hall, J. F. Perrin, N. Carboni, A. Hafner, R. Pugliese, M. Bertelsen, T. H. Rod, T. S. Richter, J. Taylor, J. C. E, H. Fangohr, C. Fortmann-Grote, T. Kluyver, R. Rosca, F. Gliksohn, L. Schrettner, Enabling Open Science for Photon and Neutron Sources, *ICALEPCS2019 Proceedings, JACoW Publishing*, 30 August **2020**, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-ICALEPCS2019-TUBPL02>

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More green open access publications are available in the PaNOSC community on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/panosc/>

PaNOSC on
zenodo

Collaboration with ExPaNDS and the ESFRI clusters

PaNOSC has been working closely with its sister project ExPaNDS, to coordinate and harmonise joint actions in management and communications, as well as for the development of the PaN research data policy framework and the services for data catalogue, analysis and simulation.

Collaboration with ESFRI cluster projects has been key to identify common challenges, share knowledge and tools, and identify common actions to better target user communities.

Main achievements

- Publication of the ESFRI clusters' position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC:
>> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3675081>
- Publication of a position paper on "EOSC – a tool for enabling Open Science in Europe" with the ESFRI clusters and European e-infrastructures;
- Contribution to EOSC Secretariat documents on EOSC sustainability (Strawman and Tinman documents).
- Joint participation in PaN user meetings and other events (ESOF 2022, ICRI 2022, EOSC Symposium, etc.).
- Video release "The DOI for data", steered by PaNOSC, and resulted from the joint effort of PaN facilities in the PaNOSC and ExPaNDS projects, and LENS and LEAPS initiatives.

WATCH THE VIDEO
The DOI for data

<https://bit.ly/DOI-for-data>

PaNOSC Partners

In collaboration with:

What the European Commission says about PaNOSC*

PaNOSC has delivered exceptional results with significant immediate or potential impact.

PaNOSC has demonstrated a great understanding of EOSC ecosystem, objectives and challenges.

The performance and ambitions have been outstanding.

Its major contribution is its impact on RIs, e-Infras, ESFRIs and national nodes in the PaN domain, promoting and facilitating the adoption of FAIR data principles.

The project has been very effectively managed, and also efficiently.

*These comments have been extracted from the EC DG-RTD General project overview consolidated report from October 2020.

PaNOSC key achievements

Visit www.panosc.eu for more information

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